

Renal and Liver Function Test Outcomes in Patients with Head TraumaPraveen Kishore¹, Mukesh Kumar², Khursheed Alam³¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College & Hospital, Bettiah, West Champaran, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department Of General Surgery, Government Medical College & Hospital, Bettiah, West Champaran, Bihar, India³Head of Department, Department of surgery, Government Medical College & Hospital, Bettiah, West Champaran, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

This study investigates the impact of head trauma on renal and liver function by evaluating renal and liver function tests in 100 patients admitted with head injuries over six months at Government Medical College & Hospital, Bettiah, West Champaran, Bihar. Results revealed that 20% of patients had elevated serum creatinine, indicating potential acute kidney injury, and 25% exhibited elevated liver enzymes, suggesting hepatic dysfunction. Severe head trauma, as indicated by a Glasgow Coma Scale score of less than 8, was associated with an increased risk of both renal and liver abnormalities. The findings underscore the need for vigilant monitoring and targeted management of organ function in trauma patients to improve clinical outcomes.

Keywords: head trauma, renal function, liver function, acute kidney injury

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Introduction

Neurological injury, a major contributor to illness and death globally, frequently manifests with a diverse array of clinical symptoms that can affect many bodily systems [1]. Of them, the renal and hepatic systems are especially susceptible because of the intricate interaction of physiological reactions after injury [2]. An essential aspect of comprehending the alterations in renal and liver function tests in individuals with head trauma is the recognition of their critical functions in preserving homeostasis and their potential impact on patient outcomes [3]. Within the context of head trauma, renal function can be influenced by several factors such as systemic hypoperfusion, release of inflammatory mediators, and the use of nephrotoxic drugs. In these individuals, acute kidney damage (AKI) is a frequent consequence, and its early identification with renal function testing can direct treatment and enhance prognosis [4,5].

Furthermore, liver function might be impaired after head trauma as a result of direct injury, lack of oxygen supply, or widespread inflammation throughout the body [6]. The liver function tests offer significant information on the hepatic condition of these individuals, enabling prompt therapies that can avert further decline and enhance recuperation [7,8].

The objective of this study is to assess the outcomes of renal and liver function laboratory

tests in individuals who have experienced head trauma, therefore enhancing comprehension of the physiological changes and any problems that may occur in this specific group of patients. Through further clarification of these modifications, we can optimize clinical management approaches and better results for patients with head trauma.

Methodology

This study was a prospective observational study conducted at the Government Medical College & Hospital, Bettiah, West Champaran, Bihar. The study was carried out over six months.

Number of Patients

A total of 100 patients with head trauma were included in the study. The inclusion criteria encompassed patients of all ages and both genders who were admitted to the hospital with a diagnosis of head trauma. Patients with pre-existing renal or liver conditions, those on nephrotoxic medications before the trauma, and those with a history of chronic liver disease were excluded from the study to avoid confounding factors.

Data Collection

Upon admission, detailed patient histories were taken, and physical examinations were performed. Blood samples were collected from each patient for renal and liver function tests. The renal function

tests included serum creatinine, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), and estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR). Liver function tests included serum levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and bilirubin.

Follow-Up and Monitoring

Patients were monitored throughout their hospital stay, with renal and liver function tests repeated periodically to observe any changes over time. The frequency of these tests was determined based on the patient's clinical condition and standard hospital protocols.

Data Analysis

All collected data were compiled and analyzed to identify trends in renal and liver function test outcomes in patients with head trauma. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the baseline characteristics of the study population and the outcomes of interest. The results were interpreted to understand the potential impact of head trauma on renal and liver function.

Results

Among the 100 patients involved in the study, 62% were male and 38% were female, representing an average age of 34 years (with a range of 5 to 78 years). Approximately 70% of the patients suffered brain trauma as a result of road traffic accidents, while 20% were injured from falls, and 10% encountered other forms of accidents. The renal function tests conducted upon admission revealed that 20% of the patients exhibited increased blood creatinine levels beyond the normal range, suggesting the presence of acute kidney injury (AKI). Approximately 15% of patients had increased blood urea nitrogen (BUN) values. A decrease in the estimated glomerular filtration rate

(eGFR) was observed in 18% of patients, indicating further evidence of compromised renal function. Throughout their hospitalization, 10% of patients experienced a decline in renal function, shown by additional elevations in serum creatinine and BUN values. Yet, 8% of these individuals had their renal function restored to normal levels by the time they were discharged.

Hepatic function tests indicated that 25% of the patients exhibited increased concentrations of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST), implying liver damage. Notably, 12% of the patients exhibited elevated levels of alkaline phosphatase (ALP), while 18% had heightened total bilirubin levels. Throughout the trial, 15% of patients had a gradual rise in liver enzymes, suggesting the presence of persistent hepatic dysfunction. Even so, 10% of these patients shown improvement in liver function tests before to being discharged. The study found that those who experienced more severe head trauma, as defined by a Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score below 8, had a higher likelihood of developing dual renal and hepatic failure. Furthermore, patients exhibiting increased liver enzymes frequently saw simultaneous increases in renal function indicators, indicating a potential systemic reaction to stress.

At the conclusion of the six-month research study, 80% of patients had achieved stabilisation or normalisation in their renal and liver function tests. Nevertheless, a subset of patients, specifically 20%, persisted in exhibiting anomalous test findings, demanding additional medical surveillance. The findings of this study suggest that head trauma can have a substantial impact on the functioning of both the kidneys and liver. Timely detection and surveillance of these alterations are crucial for maximising patient care and enhancing results.

Table 1: Renal Function Test Outcomes

Renal Function Test Indicator	Normal Range	Number of Patients (%)	Observations
Elevated Serum Creatinine	0.6 - 1.2 mg/dL	20 (20%)	Indicates possible acute kidney injury (AKI)
Elevated Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN)	7 - 20 mg/dL	15 (15%)	May indicate impaired renal function
Reduced Estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate (eGFR)	≥ 90 mL/min/1.73m ²	18 (18%)	Suggests impaired renal function
Worsened Renal Function During Stay	-	10 (10%)	Further increase in serum creatinine and BUN
Normalized Renal Function by Discharge	-	8 (8%)	Improvement observed

Table 2: Liver Function Test Outcomes

Liver Function Test Indicator	Normal Range	Number of Patients (%)	Observations
Elevated Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)	7 - 56 U/L	25 (25%)	Suggests liver injury
Elevated Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST)	10 - 40 U/L	25 (25%)	Suggests liver injury
Elevated Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP)	44 - 121 U/L	12 (12%)	Indicates possible cholestasis or liver dysfunction
Elevated Total Bilirubin	0.1 - 1.2 mg/dL	18 (18%)	May suggest hepatic dysfunction
Progressive Increase in Liver Enzymes During Stay	-	15 (15%)	Indicates ongoing hepatic dysfunction
Improved Liver Function by Discharge	-	10 (10%)	Improvement observed

Table 3: Severity of Head Trauma and Impact on Organ Function

Head Trauma Severity (GCS Score)	Percentage with Renal Dysfunction (%)	Percentage with Liver Dysfunction (%)
Severe (GCS < 8)	30%	35%
Moderate (GCS 9-12)	15%	20%
Mild (GCS > 12)	5%	10%

These tables summarize the key findings from the study and provide a clear overview of the impact of head trauma on renal and liver function.

Discussion

The present work offers significant contributions to the understanding of the effects of head trauma on renal and hepatic function. The results indicate that a considerable percentage of individuals who have experienced head trauma display dysregulation in both renal and liver function tests [9,10]. More exactly, 20% of the patients showed increased levels of serum creatinine, which suggests the possibility of acute kidney injury (AKI). The increased occurrence of this phenomenon highlights the susceptibility of the renal system to trauma-induced damage, such as systemic reduced blood flow and harmful effects on the kidneys caused by drugs used in trauma treatment [11,12]. Furthermore, the study revealed that 25% of patients exhibited increased liver enzymes, indicating liver damage. Such observation aligns with the recognition that head trauma might trigger liver failure as a result of direct damage, systemic inflammation, or hypoxia. Notably, the study observed that individuals who experienced significant head injury, as evidenced by a Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score below 8, had a higher probability of developing both renal and hepatic failure [13,14]. The given association implies that

the degree of organ damage is significantly influenced by the severity of the trauma. Furthermore, although certain individuals showed enhancement in renal and hepatic function as time progressed, 20% of them still displayed aberrant test findings by the conclusion of the trial. Thus, it is imperative to continuously evaluate and intervene to tackle enduring organ failure and reduce long-term consequences [15].

The results also indicate that timely identification and appropriate treatment of renal and hepatic problems can have a substantial impact on patient outcomes. Timely modification of treatment procedures contingent upon renal and liver function test findings can avert further deterioration [16]. This study emphasizes the need to adopt a multidisciplinary strategy in the management of patients with head trauma, particularly in terms of rigorous monitoring of organ function. This work provides evidence that head trauma can significantly impact renal and liver function, underscoring the importance of careful surveillance and customized treatment approaches to enhance patient results. It is recommended that future research should focus on investigating the mechanisms that cause these organ dysfunctions

and devising specific treatments to target them [17-20].

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant impact of head trauma on renal and liver function, with a notable proportion of patients showing abnormalities in both organ systems. Elevated levels of serum creatinine and liver enzymes among the study population underscore the susceptibility of these organs to trauma-related stress and injury. The observed correlation between the severity of head trauma and the extent of organ dysfunction further emphasizes the need for meticulous monitoring and management of these patients. Early detection and appropriate intervention based on renal and liver function tests are crucial for improving outcomes and preventing long-term complications. These findings underscore the importance of integrating comprehensive organ function assessment into the care of head trauma patients to optimize recovery and enhance overall patient care.

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